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Toward a Human-Oriented Social Engineering Defense System

Dario Pasquali^{1,2,4}, Alessandra Sciutti³, Giulio Sandini¹, Stefano Bencetti², Francesco Rea¹

¹Robotics Brains and Cognitive Sciences (RBCS), IIT

²Information and Communication Technologies directorate (ICT), IIT

³COgNiTive Architecture for Collaborative Technologies (CONTACT), IIT

⁴DIBRIS, Università di Genova

dario.pasquali@iit.it, alessandra.sciutti@iit.it, giulio.sandini@iit.it, stefano.bencetti@iit.it, francesco.rea@iit.it

Abstract

Social engineering is rising more and more concerns due to its ability to bypass traditional cyber security defense systems. In the last four years, we studied how to develop an intelligent system able to prevent humans' compliance with social engineering threats, based on the real-time assessment of humans' physiological reactions. Moreover, we explored how social robots could exploit such a system to actively support humans' decision-making. The current manuscript resumes four experiments we conducted and present the challenges we plan to tackle in the next future.

1 Introduction

For social robots to become in the future an active part of humans' society, it is crucial that they are endowed with the ability of understanding and adapting to their human partners. That's the main objective of the RBCS and CONTACT units of the Istituto Italiano di Tecnologia (Genova): using robots to investigate the sensory, motor and cognitive bases of human social skills, and integrate these abilities into a cognitive architecture on the iCub robot (Metta et al. 2008) to support its social awareness, adaptability and autonomous learning. The aim is to achieve a profound comprehension of human cognition through a constructive and embodied approach, with the technological goal of developing more intuitive and adaptable robots. In this framework, the study of trust and deception in human-robot interactions are central to this research.

1.1 Trust and Social Engineering in HRI

Hadnagy defines Social Engineering as “*any act that influences a person to take any action that may or may not be in their best interest*” (Hadnagy 2018). State-of-the-art defensive solutions traditionally rely on (i) detecting the occurrence of an attack with technical means (i.e., filtering a phishing email); or (ii) rising people awareness to make them able to discriminate a malicious interaction (Alharthi, Hammad, and Regan 2020). However, those methods may not be effective due to (i) the high variety of attacks and the difficulty to detect a spoofed interaction and (ii) the natural-

ly compliant behavior of humans when unable to discriminate what is right or wrong (Junger, Montoya, and Overink 2017). Moreover, it is proved that traditional warning vectors are not effective anymore, due to habituation effects and channel saturation (Anderson et al. 2016). The approach we propose is based on the belief that a more *human-oriented* solution could be implemented. Indeed, humans implicitly communicate more information than what they explicitly (voluntarily) do: behavioral (i.e., posture and gestures) and physiological (i.e., pupillometry, electrodermal activity, heartbeat) features are related to humans' arousal, emotion, and cognitive effort, providing an insight of individual internal state and/or motivation, besides what they can voluntarily convey. In this context human-robot interaction fits for two main reasons: (i) a social robot could be used as a vector to lead a face-to-face social engineering attack; (ii) a robot companion able to understand humans' internal state, could predict in advance the occurrence of an attack, or the compliance with a risky proposal and provide support to human fellows. In the following sections, we present our four-year research with the aim of (i) studying the evolution of trust toward robots in a long and ecological interaction (Sec. 2); (ii) understanding if a human partner is trustworthy (Sec. 3); (iii) assessing humans' implicit perception of risk and predict their compliance with social engineering threats (Sec. 4); (iv) exploring how a robot companion should intervene to support humans (Sec. 5).

2 Trust development in HRI

In this experiment, we studied how trust toward the humanoid iCub develops and evolves even in presence of unexpected behaviors of the robot. We asked 68 participants to play a treasure hunt game with iCub: they had to find 5 plastic eggs hidden in a laboratory in 20 minutes to win a monetary prize (see Fig. 1, (i)). If asked, iCub provided riddle-like hints. If they managed to find all the 5 eggs, iCub unexpectedly challenged them to bet the amount won to find a 6th egg (Aroyo et al. 2018). During the game, the robot exhibited four faulty behaviors (at predefined timings), designed to diminish its perceived reliability (Aroyo et al. 2020). With half of the participants the robot was designed to be transparent about the faults, i.e. it explained their cause after they occurred (e.g. “*my motor malfunctioned*”), (see Fig. 1, (ii)).

Figure 1, from left to right: (i) treasure hunt experimental room: (ii) iCub simulating a crash during the game; (iii) participants lying to iCub; (iv) participants playing the textual adventure with the Furhat robot.

All the participants who found the 5 eggs also accepted to gamble, mainly because the game was fun and they wanted to play more, as the majority of them reported in an informal debriefing. Post-hoc analysis shows how the number of eggs found and the frequency of hints requested was in general affected by the occurrence of faulty behaviors, but the negative impact was significantly more pronounced if the robot was transparent about the faults. Moreover, we found how being transparent about the faults decreased the trust toward the robot and the subjective evaluations of its behavior. (Aroyo et al. 2021).

3 Detect a deceptive attacker

Any social engineering attack starts with the fabrication of a credible pretext meant to gain victims’ trust. Hence, if we can understand that a human partner is lying, it could be possible to at least raise a warning about how much they are trustworthy. This could be useful to both support humans (i.e., in professions like law enforcement, caregiving, teaching) and also, to enable robots to defend themselves against malicious humans.

We enabled iCub to detect humans’ lies autonomously, during an informal human-robot interaction – a magic trick card game (see Fig 1, (ii)) – only based on humans’ pupil dilation collected in real-time with a Tobii Pro Glasses 2 eyetracker. iCub’s ability is based on a simple effect: fabrication and maintaining a credible lie requires a higher cognitive load than telling the truth. Cognitive load (along with arousal and emotion) reflects on pupil dilation; hence, the pupil dilates more while lying with respect to telling the truth (Beatty 1982; Dionisio et al. 2001). Based on this principle, we developed a heuristic method able to classify humans’ lies with an accuracy of 88.2% (Pasquali, Gonzalez-Billandon, Rea, et al. 2021). Moreover, we showed that iCub can learn how a human partner lies from a brief interaction and use this information to classify further lies and improve its knowledge with an incremental accuracy of 76.7% (Pasquali, Gonzalez-Billandon, Alexander, et al. 2021). Finally, we explored how to improve our system taking inspiration from how humans detect lies: we speculate that the cooperation between the physiological-based system adopted by iCub and the intuition-based methods of humans could be the key factor to develop a more robust and effective lie detector (Pasquali, Gaggero, et al. 2021).

4 Predict victims’ compliance

Social engineering attacks are designed to trick humans’ perception of risk and to elicit compliance. However, even if we are not rationally able to appraise the risk involved in a situation, we still experience subconscious arousal reactions that reflect on physiological proxies like pupil dilation, galvanic skin response and heartbeat. In this project, we explored how those features could be used to (i) assess humans’ risk appraisal related to social engineering threats; and (ii) to predict if they are going to comply with them.

When studying persuasion and compliance in a laboratory some experimental biases inevitably arise (Pannucci and Wilkins 2010). To mitigate them, we designed a decision-making experiment as a game-like story-driven experiment in the form of a chose-your-own-adventure (CYOA) (Green and Jenkins 2014; Kaufman and Libby 2012; Legaki et al. 2021). In CYOAs, players are asked to make several decisions that will have a concrete effect on the game itself (i.e., by revealing different narrative passages). Players pretended to be space hunters looking for a legendary treasure in a space shuttle relic. They had to survive until the end and to manage two resources: (i) *Credentials*, they had to keep secret and (ii) *Energy*, which both worked as in-game currency and health points. Participants were accompanied by iCub – a friendly Non-Playable Character (NPC) – physically present in the experimental room with them. Experimental stimuli consisted of 28 binary decisions divided into 4 conditions: *no-risk*, *risk* - inspired by (Blais and Weber 2006), social engineering threats from a virtual agent (*SE*), or social engineering threats from iCub (*SE-icub*). The latter were both inspired by (Workman 2007). The 28 decisions were distributed among the story and presented in the same order to all the participants. To better segment participants’ behavior, we instructed them to click on a “continue” button to make the possible options for each decision appear on the screen. During the interaction, we collected synchronized data from (i) a Shimmer 3 GSR+ (for galvanic skin response (GSR) and photoplethysmography (PPG)); (ii) a SR research Eyelink 1000 (for gaze, fixations, and pupil diameter); (iii) a mouse.

20 participants played our textual adventure; among them, only 2 lost the game. On average, participants complied with 68.7% (SD=16%) of the *no-risk* decisions, 45.1%

(SD=18%) of the *risk* decisions, 53.3% (SD=14%) of *SE* decision and 53.4% (SD=15%) of *SE-icub* decisions. A repeated-measures ANOVA showed a significant effect of the condition $F(19, 3) = 9.15, p < 0.001$. Due to the limited space available, we could not report the complete statistical analysis. Qualitatively, we found significant effects of the condition and the acceptance on the pupil dilation, number of fixations, number of galvanic skin response peaks and the first derivative of the galvanic skin level. Interestingly, the effects are significant even while participants are reading the textual stimulus. Then, intending to intervene to prevent the compliance with risky situations, we trained 3 random forest classifiers: (i) the first model classifies a decision as *risk/SE/SE-icub* vs *not-risky* with an F1 score of 78.4%; (ii) the second classifies a decision as *risk* vs *SE/SE-icub* with an F1 score of 82.8%; (iii) the last predict players' compliance on *risk*, *SE* and *SE-icub* decisions with an accuracy of 65%. All of them were based only on features from players' GSR, PPG, pupillometry and mouse trajectories while they were reading.

5 Robots' intervention to prevent compliance

The last, ongoing, experiment, was developed during a visiting period at the Social and Intelligent Robotics Research Laboratory (University of Waterloo, Canada). With this project, we explored different persuasion strategies a social robot could exploit to make humans change their minds against risky and social engineering decisions. We speculate a social robot could provide a more effective warning and compensate for the habituation and channel saturation issues of state-of-the-art warnings (Anderson et al. 2016). Starting from the game presented in Sec. 4, we removed *SE-icub* decisions and replaced iCub with a Furhat robot (Anon n.d.) that plays the role of narrator of the game. We chose this robot aiming at the development of a robot companion feasible to be used in everyday life (i.e., in workspaces). After each decision, the Furhat tried to persuade participants to change their mind exploiting either (i) an affective (i.e., saying "*I think you should take the other option, don't make me worry*") or (ii) a rational (i.e., saying "*I think you should give him some of your energy, because he helped you defeating the monster*"), dynamically generated based the specific situation and players' decision) persuasion strategy (Saunderson and Nejat 2019). We collected the same physiological and behavioral features listed in Sec. 4.

Currently, we are still running the data collection. From the literature (Saunderson and Nejat 2019), we speculate the affective strategy would be more effective; however, (i) this kind of experiment has never been done with decisions related to social engineering threats; and (ii) we are not only interested in the most effective strategy in absolute terms, but rather on the one that could rise participants' awareness (e.g., risk appraisal) to the right level in a specific situation. The collected physiological features will be the key factor to achieve this goal.

5 Discussion

During the last four years, we explored from different points of view the relationship between trust, social engineering, and human-robot interaction. We found how in a long and ecological human-robot interaction, humans comply with suggestions from iCub, even if it shows unexpected behaviors. The effect on performance due to the perception of the faults or the transparency suggests how the important factor is the appraisal of the risk involved in the interaction (i.e., complying with the hints of a faulty robot). Also, we speculate that the framing in which a risky proposal is posed highly influences the compliance with it; indeed, all the participants who completed the hunt (Sec. 2) also gambled the money due to the fun involved in the game. Then we explored how pupillometry, galvanic skin response and heart rate can be used to have an insight into humans' internal state (i.e., risk appraisal) and cognition (i.e., being deceptive). We proposed a minimally invasive solution based on pupillometry to detect lies in real time, autonomously, with the humanoid robot iCub. Our system can be used in informal interactions, for instance (i) to support humans in professions like law enforcement, caregiving, and education; or (ii) to enable robots to understand if a human partner is trustworthy increasing their knowledge over multiple interactions. To further improve our system and make it feasible for a real-world setup, we will need to replace the Tobii eyetracker with a camera-based solution and to increase the robustness of our classifier; for instance, by including other sources of information like speech prosody or posture and gestures. Finally, we explored whether it is possible (i) to assess humans' risk appraisal and (ii) to predict their compliance with risky or social engineering threats, based on humans' physiological reactions. Preliminary results show it is possible to have an insight on how much humans are aware of the risk involved in a situation and to predict their behavior, even if with lower accuracy. The main limitation of the current approach is the need of preprocessing and aggregating the physiological data before applying the machine learning model. In the next step, we will focus on the raw timeseries, to predict the on-line evolution of humans' risk appraisal and compliance.

In the next step, we will exploit the findings of the last two projects to develop a final experiment, tailored to a more realistic scenario. The objective is to implement an intelligent system able to support humans against real social engineering threats (i.e., phishing emails) delivering effective warnings either on-screen or via an embodied social agent (i.e., iCub). Finally, it will be necessary to tackle the ethical and privacy-related issues the intelligent system we are developing could rise; like what it should do, knowing a human partner is lying; or its potential malicious misuses (i.e., using it to lead a social engineering attack that minimizes participants risk appraisal).

6 Conclusions

Summing up, our work is a first step toward a more human-oriented defense system against social engineering

threats. The topic is controversial, and we speculate the diffusion of robots and AI-based systems in the next future will rise even more interest. However, we strongly believe it is necessary to study and explore those issues to develop a better and safer future.

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